

Knowledge Management Basic Concepts and Value Creation

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Abstract

we are living not only in the new millennium, which is in the new age. In this period, various terms such as the post-industrial era of the Information Age, the third wave or the Knowledge Society are used to describe the current situation. Regardless of the terms, most scholars believe that one of the important issues raised in this period is the concept of knowledge management, a concept that has created excitement and contributed to a lot of debate and debate. KM is a rapidly evolving approach, and it pays great attention to the recent challenges of increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of business-centric processes, along with continuous innovation. The need for knowledge management based on the growth of the perceptions of the business community comes from the fact that knowledge in enterprise performance and access to sustainable competitive advantage is considered an important element (Davenport & Grover, 2001)[1]

Keywords: knowledge management; knowledge; knowledge economy; technology.

1-Introduction

Often, technology-related books begin with a number of definitions, but the definition of knowledge management is not easy. Different authors from various perspectives, with different approaches and motivations, have defined the knowledge management. Often, knowledge management is generally defined and defined as any organization needs to have its own way of doing its tasks and activities. This definition of knowledge management includes formal knowledge, rules of programs and procedures, and intangible technical knowledge, skills, and experiences of individuals. Also, the high definition of KM involves the way organizations work, communication, position analysis, the presentation of new solutions for issues, and the development of new business practices. In addition, the above definition includes cultural, ethnic, and values and relations with suppliers and customers as well. Knowledge management includes all the ways in which an organization manages its own knowledge assets, including how to collect, store, transfer, use, update, and create knowledge (Wickramasinghe & Rubitz, 2007)[2]. The Knowledge Management Department of Texas defines knowledge management as follows: KM is the systematic and systematic process of discovering, selecting, organizing, tabling, and providing information that enhances the recognition of individuals in their area of interest. . KM helps organizations to gain insights from their experiences, and to focus their activities on storage and use of knowledge in order to be able to deal with problems, dynamic learning, strategic planning and decision making, from this knowledge. To take advantage of KM not only prevents the deterioration of intellectual and brain assets, but also continuously adds to this wealth. There are two comprehensive definitions of knowledge management:

1. Knowledge management is to achieve organizational goals by motivating knowledge workers and creating facilities for them according to the company's strategy, so that they can interpret data and information (using existing information, experience, skills, culture). Personality, personal characteristics, emotions, etc.) through the meaning of data and information.
2. KM is the explicit and systematic management of critical knowledge and processes for the creation, organization, dissemination, use and discovery of knowledge (Madhavm & Grover, 1998)[3].

2. Knowledge management concepts

Knowledge is always valuable to people. Strong and civilized cultures are often identified with their libraries. The great library of the Alexandria Museum, the British Library, etc., is the place where the knowledge of a civilization is gathered. Therefore, knowledge management is around us, which is still not widely used. We are all familiar with terms like the knowledge economy and knowledge workers. In previous periods, the key was the production of wealth, ownership and access to capital and natural resources; while today, the key to wealth is the amount of access to knowledge creation. So, a small college with new ideas can earn billions of dollars. Sometimes the felling of trees, the gold mine, or forging created wealth, now all sectors need the services to create wealth. Most corporations nowadays have realized that they were successful because of their work skills and experience, not because of the physical assets they possessed. In addition, they have realized that even if some of their products are left out of the world market, the passage of time and the change of the company's individuals is necessary (Wickramasinghe, 2005)[4].

2.1 Basic Concepts in Knowledge Management

When discussing the subject of knowledge management, knowledge definition is considered to be a necessity. Without such a definition, managers do not exactly understand what they are looking for in management and do they have such knowledge in general for management? The answer to this question, as it seems at first plain and obvious, is not easy. This issue becomes even more difficult when it comes to the knowledge of the organization. To provide a precise definition of knowledge, various issues should be examined at different levels. One of the most important aspects of knowledge management is the precise definition of knowledge, information and data .

2-1-1- Data

Data forms the first level of knowledge management, and in fact numbers, figures, charts or special attributes that are obtained from observation, experience, or calculation, and do not in themselves produce meaning. The data can be considered as raw material requirements for decision making.

2-1-2- Information

Information is the second level of knowledge management knowledge. Information includes data in a specific context, at this level; data are grouped, refined and organized so that they can be meaningful. Information is a collection of relevant data, descriptions, and related interpretations, and other issues related to the text, according to goals, events or special processes .

2-1-3-Knowledge

With the increasing role of knowledge in human life, it seems that the dependence of different aspects of life on knowledge will increase in the future. This is due to the fact that the development of knowledge has caused the complexity and enormous amount of information to challenge its rapid and effective utilization. Generally, Garda and Ritter 2000 define knowledge as follows: blended A fluid flow of core experiences, values, conceptual information, and expert insights provides a framework for evaluating and integrating new experiences and information. Knowledge develops and develops in the minds of specialists. In organizations, knowledge is not only in the documentation of the organization's experiences, efforts, processes and everyday processes. According to Isaac and Parsma, 2005, knowledge of interactions that originate in people's inward (past experiences, intuition, tendencies, information, imaginations, thoughts) and emerges from the future imagination.

Information knowledge is organized, compiled or categorized, which is comprehensive and increases awareness and understanding. The complexity of the concept of knowledge has led to different views on it. But what comes from different definitions, knowledge refers to information that has been processed through processes such as in-depth reflection and learning in the minds of individuals or groups, so raw material information is the creation of knowledge that may It is located in books, reports, computer files, Conceptual knowledge goes beyond data and information, and is referred to as the organized set of information, the practical approach associated with it, the results of its application in various decisions and its related training. Knowledge should not be confused with data. Data is raw facts, sizes, figures, and also, knowledge is more complex than information. The resulting information is structured in a meaningful way. Knowledge is the result of an interpretation of information based on personal understanding that is influenced by the personality and characteristics of the holder and, since it is based on judgment and intuition, includes beliefs, tendencies, and behaviors. The most important feature of knowledge is its uniqueness and ingenuity. Knowledge is one of the strategic assets of the organization and is considered as the main source for all types of business .

2-2. Organizational Knowledge

Each organization possesses the knowledge that it provides with services and products. This knowledge is an organization that maintains the organization in a competitive market and guarantees its survival. Since each organization consists of a set of individuals, then organizational knowledge is formed from personal knowledge. Knowledge can be attached to individuals, called "personal knowledge". Knowledge can also be found in processes, rules, systems of work, and so on, known as "group knowledge" .Knowledge in any organization can be found in the following forms: Product Knowledge - Knowledge of Specialists - Leadership Knowledge - Environmental Knowledge - Social Knowledge .Organizational Knowledge Characteristics: Unique - Value-Non-Substitute-Strategic

Knowledge is a mixture of fluidity of experiences, values, existing information, and expert and systematic approaches that provide a framework for evaluating and applying new experiences and information. Knowledge in organizations is manifested not only in its documents and its resources, but also in working practices, organizational processes,

practices and norms. The performance and activity of organizations will greatly contribute to the production of information. Organizations capture information and interact with their surroundings, turning them into knowledge. Then they combine this knowledge with their own experiences, values, and regulations, in order to gain a basis for their actions. An organization without knowledge can not organize itself and survive as a living and dynamic system. Certainly, organizations have sought to acquire knowledge and use it. Managers who make tough decisions are more likely to seek out experienced people to constantly make their knowledge available to decision makers rather than searching for information in databases. According to studies, managers receive two thirds of their knowledge and knowledge through referrals.

2-3. Data, information and knowledge relationships

Relations between data, information and knowledge are not hierarchical and absolute. Individuals and situations determine the data, information, or knowledge of the factors. But what is certain is their level of evolution, which is more knowledge and information than data.

Figure 1: Data, information and knowledge relationships

The most important role that can be attributed to KM is to consider it as a change methodology. Knowledge management, on the one hand, by attracting new knowledge into the system and, on the other hand, the effective management of those sciences can be the most important factor in changing an organization. Due to the proximity of organizational decisions and knowledge, knowledge can improve performance and, consequently, improve the quality of service organizations in general and banks in particular.

Figure 2: The Effect of Information and Knowledge on Decision-making

2.4 -Classification of Knowledge Types

Different classifications of knowledge by the owners are presented, which are summarized in brief:

Clear knowledge: knowledge that is objective and can be expressed in formal and systematic language. This type of knowledge is independent of the staff and exists in computer information systems, books, organizational documentation, and has the ability to code and express. The dialect is a form of knowledge that can easily be transmitted from one skilled person to another by oral communication or writing.

Hidden knowledge (latent): knowledge that is abstract, and finding it is not easy, its resources and content lies in the mind. This knowledge is acquired through practical experience and learning, and is, in fact, an unwritten knowledge of the organization. The phrase "man more than what he says" or "pottery" refers to hidden knowledge. Deep knowledge is in the consciousness of the unconscious, so it is difficult to describe it to others. Usually, experts can extract it.

Individual knowledge: lies in the person and rooted in his individual actions (the same).

Group knowledge (organization): lies in an organization's social and cultural systems. Many scholars, when they talk about knowledge, refer to knowledge that lies in the mind of man and is not easily identifiable and transmitted from one person to another. This type of knowledge lies in the individual's or organization's experiences, beliefs, values and culture, and has a vast, highly valuable domain and unique assets that are rarely copied by others and create a competitive advantage for individuals and Organizations are (the same).

2-5-The Conceptual Framework for Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is one of the branches of knowledge economy; knowledge management completely introduces a new concept and a new management approach. This concept operates on the transformation of the rational benefits of employees and the organization of the beneficial forces of the members of the staff of the force of competition and new value. Knowledge management focuses on linking information with information, information with activities and information with a person to realize knowledge sharing (such as tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge) and is totally different from information management. Traditional library functions; collecting, processing, disseminating, storing, utilizing document information in order to provide service to the community. In the era of knowledge economics, the library as a treasure of human knowledge will contribute to the development of knowledge and the important link in the chain of knowledge progression. In the twenty-first century, libraries will inevitably face a new issue of knowledge management. Knowledge management in libraries should focus on the research and development of knowledge, the creation of a knowledge base, exchange and knowledge sharing among library staff (including its users), training library staff, expediting the explicit processing of non-explicit knowledge and realizing its subscription.

In most definitions of knowledge management, the process of using knowledge has been mentioned more than all, and the knowledge creation as the main element has been discussed more slowly. While knowledge management can play an effective role in society that succeeds in producing and creating knowledge. Here are some of these definitions:

- Turban KM organizes knowledge creation and distribution and makes it possible to use it in the organization.
- Baron considers knowledge management as a systematic and integrated approach for recognizing, using, and sharing in unconsidered and untapped expertise and expertise in the organization.

According to Handley, KM is a general description of the culture, processes, infrastructure, and technologies existing in an organization that allows the attraction, growth, and optimization of the knowledge capital of the organization to achieve strategic goals.

- Kuzmin considers knowledge management as a process of attracting and gaining knowledge by experts, experts, and professionals in the organization, which results in the group gaining authority, credibility and independence in managing the organization, and their knowledge in Provide management with equal pay. Knowledge management is the area in which the managers of organizations and knowledge forces play a part, and the ideal state is created when this knowledge is stored and used for the purposes of the organization.

- The Specialist Quality and Participation Magazine also provides a definition of knowledge management that is prudent. Knowledge management, guidance and counseling to deal with critical and critical issues of the organization in terms of adaptability and survival in the changing environment. Basically, knowledge management is a crystallization and visualization of a set of organizational processes that combines and integrates information, data and information capabilities, and the capabilities of innovation and creativity of organization members.

Stewart, in a general description of praise of knowledge and knowledge, considers knowledge to be a powerful source of natural and physical resources, huge factories and big banks, and believes that organizations need only to develop their mental and knowledge powers for growth and survival. To develop. From his point of view, the capital of wisdom and knowledge is the real capital of the organization, and its management is decisive for the organization. Managers should include capital knowledge as an important item in their financial statements and transform the basis of comparison from monetary wealth and financial assets to wisdom and knowledge assets, which will then be successful organizations. Not only because of wealth, but also because of the knowledge of capital .

- Russia and its colleagues are familiar with knowledge management by defining knowledge capital. From the point of view of Russian capital, knowledge is a place for thinking, dialogue, and action about the future of organizations. Only with the help of this capital can you manage the organization in the future and remain stable in the field of competition. Knowledge capital establishes the relationship between the customers and the stakeholders of the organization with the knowledge and expertise of the members of the organization in an optimal way. Management of this capital, ie, knowledge management, a set of measures and measures that help to grow and exploit .

Taylor knows the management of knowledge as a movement and movement that will make the future of the future.

- Brodock uses knowledge management and applies a range of scientific concepts and frameworks.

- Skye Rome, inspired by Stewart's writings, has invested knowledge in the hidden and hidden assets of organizations that can be achieved with a significant competitive advantage through its management and administration.

- Manage the knowledge management process by organizing, selecting, organizing, refining and providing information in a manner that improves and enhances understanding of organizational members and enhances organizational memory and helps the organization learn from its experiences .

As mentioned above, knowledge management is often interpreted as a process for the deployment, acquisition, and distribution of knowledge, and the discovery of knowledge, which is the most valuable element of knowledge management, has been neglected or understated. In the age of knowledge, productivity has become newly defined and productivity is the criterion of productivity before producing the subject of productivity. The universe has said that "knowledge management" is an attempt to exploit knowledge and "knowledge", to discover and to receive the unknowns and ignorant ones. Knowledge is the main element and the pillar of knowledge management, and managers' efforts should focus on the creation and production of knowledge.

With these interpretations, knowledge management can be summarized as follows: "KM is a systematic approach to finding, understanding, and using knowledge to achieve organizational goals, and to create, by reducing the time and cost of testing and error or repetition. Worth It.

With these definitions it is determined that knowledge management is a range of activities that are used to manage, exchange, create, or promote intellectual capital at a macro level. Knowledge management is the clever design of processes, tools, structures, etc., with the intention of increasing, renovating, sharing or improving the use of knowledge, which appears in each of the three elements of intellectual capital, namely, structural, human and social. Knowledge management is a process that helps organizations identify, select, organize and publish important information and skills that are considered as organizational memory and typically not organized. This enables effective management of organizations to solve learning problems, strategic planning and dynamic decision making .

2-6. Knowledge management

In recent years, knowledge management has become one of the most interesting and challenging subjects in business management, and its application circle has always been wider with other topics in the field of management. Knowledge management is a process that helps organizations identify, select, organize, disseminate and transfer important information and skills that are part of the history of the organization and are generally structurally unrelated to the organization. Organizations must pay attention to everything because knowledge management acts as a work strategy at the same time throughout the organization and is a tool for the development of an organization's overall program. Knowledge management is a complicated process and its effective implementation requires a clear, transparent understanding of factors that affect the knowledge management process. Indeed, the key to understanding the success and failure of knowledge management in an organization is to recognize and create the appropriate conditions for the effective implementation of knowledge management processes. Among the various infrastructures required to effectively carry out KM actions, human-societal factors play a crucial and decisive role. Knowledge management is a process that helps organizations to find, select, organize and publish important information. Specialized knowledge management is essential for activities such as solving dynamic learning problems, strategic

planning and decision making. Knowledge management is based on a new way of thinking about the organization and sharing of intellectual resources and a method for productivity and performance improvement. In this management, attention is paid to optimizing organizational knowledge for increasing performance through various procedures. In today's competitive world, knowledge has become the strategic source of many organizations. In 1994, Nonaka classified knowledge into two forms: tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge[5]. KM refers to efforts systematically to find, create, access, use and invest in intangible organizations, enhance continuous learning culture and knowledge sharing in the organization. Knowledge management is related to the creation and development of knowledge assets of the organization and is related to the identification, creation, application and sharing of knowledge. The ultimate goal of knowledge management is the application of knowledge to improve organizational performance. Leadership approach in KM requires the deployment of a military that treats each employee as valuable and creates a knowledge leader one by one. The implementation of this environmental system facilitates employees' efforts in applying knowledge leadership and provides rewards in the knowledge management process and provides employees with the task of taking decisions without the need for supervisors from their heads of departments.

2-7. The causes of knowledge management

1. The transformation of the industrial business model, where the assets of an organization were essentially tangible and financial capital (production facilities, machinery, land, etc.) towards organizations whose main assets were unobtrusive, with knowledge, expertise, ability, and management They are tied to the creativity of their employees.

2. The extraordinary increase in the amount of information, its electronic storage, and the increase in access to information in general has increased the value of knowledge, because it is only through the knowledge that this information is valuable, knowledge is also high. Because it is closer to action. Information alone does not make a decision, but information is transformed into knowledge based on human beings that leads to decision and therefore action.

3- Change the age pyramid of the population and the demographic characteristics mentioned in only a few sources. Many organizations have found that a large amount of their important knowledge is on the brink of retirement. There is an increasing awareness that, if not measured and appropriately done, much of this vital knowledge will simply go away from the organization.

4. Specialization of activities may also entail the risk of loss of organizational knowledge and expertise through the transfer or dismissal of employees.

At the beginning, knowledge management was considered only from the technological point of view, and it was considered a technology. However, organizations gradually found that something beyond the management of information was needed for real use of employee skills. Human beings are at the center of the development, implementation, and success of knowledge management in the face of technology and electronics, and this human factor is the key to distinguishing knowledge management from the same concepts as information management.

3. The Quad Management Process of Knowledge

Tacouchi and Nonaka introduced four processes in 2000 to create knowledge in each organization[8], based on the link between tacit and obvious knowledge:

- Socialization: Dividing or disseminating tacit knowledge between individuals, usually through joint activities, not through written or oral instructions, for example, for the transfer of ideas and Imagination is represented by the method of a master-student approach to newcomers. The knowledge is created in a group environment that is accomplished both through the acquisition of complete individual knowledge and through the sharing of common understanding. Takes place. Social processes play an important role in transferring knowledge from person to group. The sharing of tacit knowledge is directly obtained from others through shared experiences, reviews, imitations, and so on. Often, tacit sharing explains tacit knowledge even without language. This method is common in the collective behavior of the Japanese. [9]

- Extraction: Express the tacit knowledge and make it understandable, making it easier to understand. For example, the conventional learning methodology at universities requires the extraction of professors' knowledge as a first step in the process of student learning. In addition, extrapolation involves techniques that help people's ideas and ideas in the form of words, concepts, visual language or imagination (eg, metaphor, analogy, description) and deductive / deductive arguments, or Creative Inference. The extraction and storage of raw knowledge is also called extrapolation, as Farapaolo finds and manages information and other analytical and processing abilities at this stage. In fact, in this

case tacit knowledge is often transformed into explicit knowledge through the use of metaphors and analysis (the use of particular languages) . [11]

Internalization: Transforming explicit knowledge into the tacit knowledge of an organization that individuals must define their own knowledge in explicit organizational knowledge. In internalization processes, obvious knowledge may be put into action and practice, so that acquiring individual knowledge can be based on the re-experience of the work others have done. In another way, people can acquire tacit knowledge in virtual situations or by studying and paying attention to the speeches and stories of others, or from experience through simulation or test. Learning through work, in-service training, learning through observation and face-to-face meetings are some of the internalization processes by which individuals acquire knowledge. Alan Radding (1998)[6] considers it a process of collecting knowledge collected to extract and transfer information of a particular knowledge seeker, and considers this process to be an advanced knowledge of the knowledge. For example, complex knowledge may not be presented as a list of integral data points, but rather as a rich graphic that reveals relationships and insights at a glance. In this case, explicit knowledge is returned in the form of tacit knowledge, if people internalize it as "practical learning". Therefore, learning as much as mental must be physical.

Combining: Transforming explicit knowledge into a set of more obvious knowledge is more complex. Focusing on communication, decomposition, integration, diffusion, knowledge system, and composition; helping to increase knowledge at the level of the group and organization. Innovative organizations are seeking new, developed concepts that are created, moderated, and modeled at organizational and inter-organizational levels. In addition, complex organizational processes require the collaboration of different groups within the organization, and the combination of these activities supports and supports the integration of a set of knowledge and technology. The justification of the concepts and the construction of the main pattern is through the systematic design of concepts in a set of different forms of explicit knowledge.

4. Knowledge management and its strategic role in empowering employees

The growth of information and knowledge in recent years has been very rapid and exponential. From this perspective, the present age has been called the age of information explosion, so that 80% of the technology and knowledge findings, as well as 90% of all knowledge and technical information It is produced in the world in the twentieth century. At the same time, it doubles every five and a half times; on the other hand, many of them are dated in less than 4 years.

Unlike new products, knowledge can be a sustainable advantage. Ultimately, all competitors, prices, and quality of their products tend to be well-liked in the market and to the quality level and prices of leading companies, but the companies benefiting from knowledge management and the richness of science, a higher staircase and a higher degree of quality, innovation and efficiency will be achieved. Because they also make a larger profit for the company and they can continue to operate in a special procedure. Unlike material capital, which is reduced if its value is used, the value of knowledge capital increases with its use. Knowledge-based companies do not lose sight of new ideas, but they create new thinking and improve the level of performance of their forces. The focus of knowledge management activities is on the application of knowledge that has been learned from the most effective components of this management. In other words, the entire focus of knowledge management is that knowledge used in organizations is used to lead to the profitability of the organization. Unfortunately, the importance and the importance of the knowledge that ensures that it is not at any time in the organization's activities. In this case, there are steps to measure implicit knowledge and available skills. The combination of daily tasks with tasks related to knowledge management, the support of top managers, and the use of knowledge, will be effective in competing and increasing efficiency, and will create creativity and innovation in the staff, empower them, and ultimately create a learning organization. The empowerment and sustainable development of employees is the key to continuously improving the quality of products and services for our customers. Therefore, it can be said that effective factors in the process of empowerment of information workers, knowledge and professional skills are obtained in the context of knowledge management. In order to provide this factor, there are possibilities to develop professional skills in the organization, the existence of efficient and effective training in the organization and having technical and specialized information related to posts can be useful.

5. Summary and Conclusion

Knowledge of capital is used to help optimize other operational assets. Knowledge of knowledge is the intelligence of man and the human being is the other beings. Knowledge capital differs from other market capitalization because it can be used by many when it is created without being diminished and can be considered as non-exclusive. The knowledge capital is inseparable, and when it is published, one can no longer exclude others, in other words, it can be

said that the time of knowledge becomes valuable to be published and exploited. In summary, effective management of knowledge capital in an organization is the most sustainable source of development.

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